

RETIREMENT RESOURCES, SELF-COMPASSION AND RETIREMENT ANXIETY IN PRE-RETIREMENT INDIVIDUALS

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to examine the relationship between retirement resources, self-compassion, and retirement anxiety in individuals approaching retirement. The main aims of the study were to determine the relationship between retirement resources and retirement anxiety; to examine the association of self-compassion with retirement anxiety; and to assess the mediating role of self-compassion in the relationship between retirement resources and retirement anxiety. The sample comprised 170 government employees in the pre-retirement phase aged between 55 and 59 years ($M = 57.19$, $SD = 1.44$), recruited using purposive sampling. The instruments used were the Sociodemographic Questionnaire, the Retirement Resources Inventory (Leung & Earl, 2012), the Self-Compassion Scale–Short Form (Neff, 2003), and the Nigerian Pre-retirement Anxiety Scale (Ugwu et al., 2019). The findings revealed significant negative relationships between retirement resources, self-compassion, and retirement anxiety. Among the subscales of retirement anxiety, physical, social, and cognitive resources were found to significantly reduce anxiety related to financial preparedness, social obligation, and social alienation. Subcomponents of self-compassion such as self-kindness, mindfulness, and common humanity were also found to be negatively associated with retirement anxiety, while over-identification and isolation were positively associated. Hierarchical regression indicated that both retirement resources and self-compassion significantly predicted levels of retirement anxiety. Furthermore, mediation analysis confirmed that self-compassion partially mediated the relationship between retirement resources and retirement anxiety. These results were interpreted in the context of existing literature, the Resource-Based Dynamic Model of Retirement Adjustment, and the cultural context of Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Retirement, a milestone previously regarded as one of rest and reward, is now increasingly accompanied by stress due to concerns over financial, social, and psychological readiness (Fletcher et al., 2020; Hershey & Henkens, 2014). For pre-retirees, worries of losing structure,

identity, and resources tend to exacerbate stress during this life transition (Topa et al., 2018). More recent studies have turned attention toward both external resources of retirement, ie, financial sufficiency and social support, and internal psychological resources that may protect against

retirement stress. One of those psychological resources is self-compassion, which includes treating the self with kindness in the midst of stress, acknowledging one's experience as something inherent to the human condition, and staying in balance (Neff, 2003). Self-compassion has been related to greater emotional strength, skillful coping, and psychological health in aging adults (Allen et al., 2012; Homan, 2016), implying that it may be important in how one perceives and utilizes resources in retirement.

According to Henning et al. (2020) and Lindwall et al. (2017), retirement is a significant life shift marked by role changes, a reduction in daily social engagement, lack of routine, and the transition from working to not working. Retirement has been linked to an individual's entry into their third age (Laslett, 1991; Lindwall et al., 2017). Robert Atchley (1976) described retirement as occurring in five stages: honeymoon, disenchantment, reorientation, stability, and termination.

Retirement resources are the material and immaterial resources that are accessible to individuals in enabling them to acclimate to retirement and ensure well-being in this new stage of life (Wang et al., 2011). These include financial resources, social support, health status, psychological strength, and purposeful activities. Their availability and perception greatly impact post-retirement adjustment and levels of anxiety (Hershey & Henkens, 2014). Wang and Shultz (2010) proposed a resource dynamic model of adjustment to retirement, highlighting that the quality of post-retirement life depends significantly on access and preservation of physical, cognitive, motivational, financial, social, and emotional resources. Decrease or deficiency in these resources was related to heightened retirement anxiety and less well-being (Topa et al., 2018).

The Resource-Based Dynamic Model developed by Wang et al. (2011) served as the theoretical foundation for this study, explaining retirement adjustment as a function of changes in resources over time. This model has been utilized in previous research to understand how resource changes during the retirement transition affect psychological outcomes (Yeung, 2018; Záhorcová et al., 2021).

Globally, retirement resources are strained due to aging populations and inadequate savings, with low confidence in retirement wealth sufficiency (Investopedia, 2025a; Investopedia, 2016). In South Asia, pension coverage remains limited, and the situation is particularly alarming in Pakistan, where only approximately 3% of seniors receive pensions, primarily through the Employees' Old-Age Benefits Institution (Wikipedia, 2025; MDPI, 2024; NCBI, 2022).

Self-compassion, as conceptualized by Neff (2003), consists of self-kindness, common humanity, and mindfulness, with their opposing components being self-judgment, isolation, and over-identification. Self-compassion increases emotional resilience and adaptive coping, particularly during life transitions such as retirement, and may influence how individuals evaluate and respond to their available resources (Allen et al., 2012; Homan, 2016). Individuals high in self-compassion are less likely to catastrophize perceived resource deficits and more likely to engage in proactive coping behaviors.

Research indicates that self-compassion is associated with reduced stress and better emotional adjustment in older adults (Allen et al., 2012; Homan, 2016), and a meta-analysis by Zessin et al. (2015) reaffirmed its positive association with well-being. Self-compassion has also been shown to mitigate retirement-related stressors such as loss of identity, reduced socialization, and financial concerns by promoting healthy self-reflection and reducing maladaptive rumination (Raes, 2010).

Retirement anxiety refers to emotional distress experienced in anticipation of retirement and is influenced by concerns related to financial security, social integration, health, and loss of purpose (Fletcher et al., 2020; Topa & Alcover, 2015). Fletcher et al. (2020) emphasized the social components of retirement anxiety, including fears of social exclusion and loss of usefulness, highlighting that retirement anxiety is shaped by both objective resources and subjective perceptions of preparedness (Topa et al., 2018).

International research suggests that 40–60% of individuals experience moderate to severe retirement anxiety (Topa et al., 2018). In Pakistan,

this anxiety is intensified by weak pension systems and cultural expectations of family caregiving, with approximately 70% of elderly individuals reporting concerns about financial dependence and inadequate healthcare (Rafique & Saeed, 2022).

Literature Review

The current chapter provides a critical review of the literature on retirement anxiety and its relationships to psychological and contextual factors in pre-retirement individuals. The review is particularly concerned with how self-compassion and resources in retirement influence anxiety about retirement. Using theoretical models and empirical research, this chapter examines how various forms of internal psychological resilience such as self-compassion and external forms such as emotional, financial and social resources intersect to affect retirement related outcomes.

Retirement adjustment is a multidimensional process influenced by psychological as well as resource-related factors. Research suggests that retirement experiences are shaped not merely by the end of work but by available resources and psychological traits (Joo et al., 2023). Retirement resources such as financial stability, social support, health, and time organization contribute positively to well-being, with effects mediated by Sense of Coherence (Antonovsky). Active leisure activities further moderate adjustment by enhancing identity, purpose, and social connectedness (Joo et al., 2023).

Osborne (2012) highlighted key psychological challenges during retirement, including identity disturbance, decisional paralysis, and loss of workplace social structures. Approximately one-third of retirees experience significant adjustment difficulties, emphasizing the importance of emotional and social preparation alongside financial planning.

Self-compassion has emerged as a vital psychological resource in later life, promoting emotional regulation, reducing distress, and enhancing well-being. Phillips (2013) demonstrated positive associations between self-compassion, ego integrity, meaning in life, and positive affect, while Smith (2015) found self-

compassion to be linked with lower depression, stress, and improved health in older adults. These findings highlight the role of self-compassion in supporting resilience and successful aging.

Retirement anxiety is an emerging focus in gerontological research, particularly in contexts marked by financial insecurity and limited institutional support. Adejare et al. (2019) identified financial vulnerability, identity loss, and psychological challenges as key sources of anxiety among prospective retirees, emphasizing the importance of pre-retirement counselling. Ugwu et al. (2024) reported mixed associations between retirement anxiety and life satisfaction, highlighting the role of contextual and cultural factors. Ugwu et al. (2021) further identified proactive personality, social support, and subjective career success as buffers against pre-retirement anxiety.

Research on retirement conceptualization and planning demonstrates that individuals' meanings attached to retirement influence planning behaviors and adjustment. Bačová et al. (2024) showed that viewing retirement as a new beginning or imposed disruption was positively related to retirement planning. Noone (2009) emphasized psychosocial planning and interpersonal communication as critical to well-being in retirement, while Hyde et al. (2004) demonstrated that occupational inequalities persist into retirement, shaping health and economic outcomes.

Studies by Zeka (2017) and Yeung et al. (2017) further underscore the importance of proactive, multidimensional retirement planning. Financial preparedness, psychosocial planning, and resource accumulation prior to retirement were consistently associated with positive attitudes, lower anxiety, and improved post-retirement well-being. Yeung et al. (2017), drawing on the Resource-Based Dynamic Model (Wang et al., 2011), emphasized the cultural relevance of family-inclusive planning in collectivist societies.

Overall, the literature indicates that retirement adjustment is shaped by both external resources and internal psychological strengths. While financial readiness and planning reduce anxiety, personality traits, social support, and positive

retirement conceptualizations further ease transition. Despite growing attention to structural resources, intrinsic psychological assets such as self-compassion remain underexplored in retirement research. Integrating self-compassion into retirement preparation may enhance coping, reduce anxiety, and support healthier transitions. In conclusion, retirement adjustment is influenced by economic, social, and psychological factors. Planning, voluntary retirement, meaningful post-retirement activities, and positive retirement perceptions contribute to well-being and reduced anxiety. Although much research emphasizes external preparations, the literature highlights the critical role of internal emotional resources, particularly self-compassion, in fostering resilience and successful aging.

Rationale of the Study

Retirement is increasingly recognized as a major psychological, social, and economic transition. While prior research has emphasized financial and institutional preparation, limited attention has been given to intrinsic psychological resources such as self-compassion, particularly in South Asian contexts where institutional support is limited. This study addresses this gap by examining how self-compassion interacts with retirement resources to influence retirement anxiety.

This research contributes to gerontological psychology by focusing on pre-retirement anxiety, positioning self-compassion as a protective factor, and examining retirement resources as multidimensional constructs. By exploring the interaction between intrinsic and extrinsic factors, the study provides insights relevant to workplace planning, public policy, and community interventions aimed at promoting well-being and reducing anxiety during the transition to retirement.

Aims of the Study

- To explore the relationship between retirement resources and retirement anxiety in individuals nearing retirement.

- To examine the relation between self-compassion and retirement anxiety in individuals in pre-retirement phase.
- To investigate whether self-compassion and retirement resources act as protective factors in lowering retirement anxiety in individuals concerning over retirement.

Hypotheses

H1: Retirement resources are likely to be negatively correlated with retirement anxiety in pre-retirement individuals.

- Higher physical resources are likely to predict greater financial preparedness related retirement anxiety.
- Higher social resources are likely to predict lower social obligation related retirement anxiety.
- Higher social resources are likely to predict lower social alienation related retirement anxiety.

H2: Self-compassion is likely to be negatively correlated with retirement anxiety in pre-retirement individuals.

- Higher self-kindness is likely to predict greater financial preparedness related retirement anxiety.
- Higher over-identification is likely to predict lower financial preparedness related retirement anxiety.
- Higher over-identification is likely to predict greater social obligation related retirement anxiety.
- Higher over-identification is likely to predict greater social alienation related retirement anxiety.
- Higher common humanity is likely to predict lower social alienation related retirement anxiety.
- Higher mindfulness is likely to predict greater financial preparedness related retirement anxiety.
- Higher mindfulness is likely to predict lower social obligation related retirement anxiety.

- Higher mindfulness is likely to predict lower social alienation related retirement anxiety.
- H3: Self-compassion is likely to mediate the relationship between retirement resources and retirement anxiety.
- Self-kindness is likely to positively mediate the relationship between physical resources and financial preparedness.
 - Over-identification is likely to negatively mediate the relationship between physical resources and financial preparedness.
 - Over-identification is likely to negatively mediate the relationship between cognitive resources and financial preparedness.

- Over-identification is likely to negatively mediate the relationship between physical resources and social obligation.
- Over-identification is likely to negatively mediate the relationship between cognitive resources and social obligation.
- Over-identification is likely to negatively mediate the relationship between physical resources and social alienation.
- Over-identification is likely to negatively mediate the relationship between cognitive resources and social alienation.
- Mindfulness is likely to positively mediate the relationship between physical resources and social alienation.

Proposed Model

Figure 1.1

Proposed Model showing the relationship between retirement resources and retirement anxiety through the mediating role of self-compassion.

Methodology

This section comprises of the research design and sampling strategy used to conduct the present research study.

Research Design

A correlational research design was used to find out the relationship between retirement resources, self-compassion and retirement anxiety. Correlational research involves collecting data to determine whether and to what degree a

relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables (Gay, Mills, & Airasian, 2012, p. 204).

Sampling Strategy

The participants were taken through purposive sampling strategy. Purposive sampling represents a non-probability sampling method where participants with specific qualities or attributes pertinent to research needs are chosen (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016). This sampling process allows only those persons meeting criteria e.g., reaching the stage of pre-retirement, to participate in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Individuals aged 55-59 years approaching retirement.
- Individuals currently working in government sector.

Exclusion Criteria

- Those who have never held traditional employment (e.g., lifelong freelancers, entrepreneurs).
- Those who have a terminal illness.

Sample Characteristics

The study comprised a sample of 170 pre-retiree participants between 55 and 59 years old, slightly more than G-Power's recommended sample size of 166 to achieve adequate statistical power for regression analysis with medium effect size, $\alpha = .05$, and power $(1-\beta) = .80$. This provided ample statistical power and compensated for any likely data loss or data inconsistencies. Participants were drawn from diverse professional backgrounds, including banks, universities, and government offices across Lahore, ensuring broad representation of the urban pre-retirement population. The sample (N = 170) characteristics are described in the table.

Table 2.1

Table showing sample characteristics N=170

Characteristics	n	%	M(SD)
Age			57.19(1.44)
Years of Service			29.33(4.23)
Time left in Retirement			2.81(1.43)
Gender			
Male	111	65.3	
Female	59	34.7	
Education			
Matric	2	1.2	
BA	37	21.8	
MA	53	31.2	
MSc	12	7.1	
MBA	7	4.1	
MPhil	30	17.6	
MBBS	1	0.6	
PhD	28	16.5	
Marital Status			
Married	164	96.5	
Unmarried	3	1.8	
Widowed	3	1.8	
Other Sources of Income			
Yes	52	30.6	
No	118	69.4	
Number of Scale			

15 th Scale	9	5.3
16 th Scale	27	15.9
17 th Scale	40	23.5
18 th Scale	45	26.5
19 th Scale	49	28.8
Socio-economic Status		
Upper	27	15.9
Middle	140	82.4
Lower	3	1.8
Physical Illness		
Yes	21	12.4
No	149	87.6
Specify		
BP	5	2.9
Cholesterol	2	1.2
Diabetes	7	4.1
Heart	4	2.4
Joint Pain	1	0.6
None	151	88.8
Post-retirement Planning		
Yes	30	17.6
No	140	82.4

Note. n=frequency, %=percentage, M=mean, SD=standard deviation

Operational Definitions

Retirement Resources

Retirement resources are regarded as the “tangible and intangible assets that individuals can draw upon to support them in adjusting to retirement,” encompassing financial, social, emotional, cognitive, motivational, and physical domains (Leung & Earl, 2012, p. 188).

Self-Compassion

Self-compassion is “being receptive to and moved by one's own suffering, feeling affectionate and gentle toward oneself, taking an embracing, nonjudgmental attitude toward one's deficiency and failure, and recognizing that one's own experience is common to human existence” (Neff, 2003, p. 224).

Pre-retirement Anxiety

Pre-retirement anxiety is defined as a “state of worry or unease experienced by individuals nearing retirement, often characterized by worries about financial security, loss of identity,

diminished social networks, and uncertainty about the future” (Ugwu et al., 2019, p. 65).

Measures

Sociodemographic Questionnaire

A sociodemographic questionnaire was made for categorization of the participants and for accounting potential confounding factors that may influence the relationship between variables under investigation. Participants were assigned numbers instead of names. It included demographic variables such as age, government scale, years of service, income level, and previous retirement planning.

Retirement Resources Inventory (Leung & Earl, 2012)

The Retirement Resources Inventory (RRI) is a 35-item scale designed to assess resources available during the transition to retirement. It measures physical, cognitive, and social resources using a Likert-type scale. Physical resources assess health, fitness, and monetary assets; cognitive resources measure planning, flexibility, and problem-solving abilities; and social resources assess social support,

interpersonal relationships, and involvement. The RRI demonstrates high internal reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.92$) and good construct validity, with strong correlations with retirement satisfaction and adjustment.

Self-Compassion Scale Short Form (Neff, 2003)

The Self-Compassion Scale Short Form (SCS-SF) is a 12-item instrument developed from the original 26-item scale by Neff (2003). It measures six subscales: self-kindness, self-judgment, common humanity, isolation, mindfulness, and over-identification, rated on a 5-point Likert scale. The SCS-SF demonstrates good internal reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha \approx 0.86$; Raes et al., 2011) and good construct validity, with associations to higher psychological well-being and lower anxiety and depression. The scale retains strong psychometric qualities and is suitable for time-restricted studies.

Nigerian Pre-retirement Anxiety Scale (Ugwu et al., 2019)

The Nigerian Pre-retirement Anxiety Scale (NPAS) is a measure of retirement anxiety grounded in Cognitive-Behavioral Theory. It consists of three subscales: financial preparedness, social obligation, and social alienation. The scale has demonstrated good internal reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.82$) and established content and construct validity (Ugwu et al., 2021). The NPAS is relevant for the Pakistani context due to similar socio-cultural and economic factors influencing retirement anxiety and provides a multidimensional assessment of retirement-related concerns.

Translation of Assessment Measures

All the measures applied in this study were translated into Urdu in line with the standardized steps described in the MAPI Research Trust guidelines for research instrument linguistic validation (MAPI Research Trust, 2017). The use of the MAPI guidelines aimed at preserving psychometric integrity and cultural sensitivity in the instruments among the target population.

Forward Translation

Forward translation was conducted to ensure linguistic and conceptual accuracy. Three BS Clinical Psychology students proficient in English and Urdu independently translated the measures from English to Urdu. The translations were reviewed by the research supervisor, and the most contextually relevant versions were compiled while remaining consistent with the original measures.

Backward Translation

After forward translation, backward translation was performed to check accuracy and equivalence between the Urdu and original English versions. Another BS Clinical Psychology student, with no prior exposure to the original scale, independently back-translated the Urdu version into English. This process minimized bias and allowed comparison for discrepancy, meaning loss, or culturally inappropriate terms. Upon confirming close resemblance in meaning and psychological intention, the Urdu version was finalized for use in the study.

Procedure

After approval from the Doctoral Program Committee, formal permissions were obtained from the original authors of the scales for their use and Urdu translation. The translation was conducted according to standardized guidelines, and a sociodemographic information sheet was developed. The translated scales and sociodemographic sheet were compiled into a complete questionnaire.

A pilot study was conducted before the main study to refine procedures (Bowling, 2009). Ten participants meeting inclusion criteria completed the questionnaire, reported no difficulties, and their data were retained.

For the main study, informed consent was obtained and participants were informed of their rights. The final sample comprised 170 pre-retiree participants aged 55–59 years from government offices, banks, and educational institutions. Only consenting participants fulfilling inclusion criteria were recruited, while refusals were respectfully excluded.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association (APA) were followed throughout all phases of the research. Permission was granted from the Departmental Doctoral Program Committee, authors of the original measures (including Urdu translation), and heads of government offices, banks, and institutes. Informed consent was obtained after explaining the purpose of the study, voluntary participation, and the right to withdraw. Participants were assured of confidentiality, academic use of data only, and anonymity through coded identifiers.

Results

Table 3.1

Table showing psychometric properties of scales and subscales (N=170)

Scale/Subscale	N	M	SD	Range	Cronbach's α
Retirement Resources	35	86.61	9.99	54-112	0.73
Physical Resources	8	31.76	5.28	17-40	0.76
Social Resources	9	17.27	3.65	9-30	0.65
Cognitive Resources	18	37.58	6.19	20-59	0.66
Retirement Anxiety	15	52.28	5.59	29-73	0.61
Financial Preparedness	5	10.58	3.15	6-25	0.58
Social Obligation	6	25.53	3.57	10-30	0.79
Social Alienation	4	16.16	2.86	6-20	0.75
Self-Compassion	12	34.76	3.69	25-51	0.67
Self-Kindness	2	8.19	1.59	2-10	0.62
Self-Judgement	2	4.16	1.86	2-10	0.68
Common Humanity	2	5.46	1.92	2-10	0.54
Isolation	2	5.02	1.55	2-9	0.61
Mindfulness	2	8.39	1.45	2-10	0.42
Over-identification	2	3.54	1.49	2-8	0.56

Note. N=No. of items, M=mean, SD=standard deviation, α =cronbach's alpha.

Retirement Resources Inventory (Leung & Earl, 2012) demonstrated satisfactory internal consistency for the overall scale ($\alpha = .73$), indicating that the items were significantly related enough to measure the overall construct of retirement resources.

Retirement Anxiety Scale (Ugwu et al., 2019) showed low internal consistency for the overall scale ($\alpha = .61$), which, although below the ideal threshold, is acceptable for recently created or environment-adapted measures.

Self-Compassion Scale Short Form (Neff, 2003) showed acceptable overall reliability ($\alpha = .67$),

This chapter aimed at examining the impact of retirement resources on retirement anxiety and the mediation role of self-compassion among individuals at the pre-retirement phase. This section introduces the statistical analysis utilized to achieve the research objectives and hypotheses.

Reliability Analysis

Measures used in this study demonstrated sound internal reliability. Cronbach's alpha was calculated through SPSS to assess item consistency, with values above .70 considered acceptable and above .60 satisfactory for exploratory research (Field, 2018).

indicating that the 12 items, despite low internal consistency, are usable at this emerging developmental phase of research.

Correlation Analysis

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation is a statistical technique used to assess the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two continuous variables, with coefficients (r) ranging from -1 to +1, where values closer to ± 1 indicate stronger relationships and values near 0 indicate weak or no association. This method assumes normally distributed data and linear, homoscedastic relationships (Field, 2018). It was

employed to examine correlations between main study variables and potential demographic covariates.

Table 3.2

Correlation between Demographic Characteristics (Covariates), Subscales of Retirement Resources, Self-Compassion and Retirement Anxiety (N=170)

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1. Phy.Rs	31.76	5.28	—														
2. Soc.Rs	17.27	3.65	-.10	—													
3. Cog.Rs	37.58	6.19	.11	.37**	—												
4. Sel.Kd	8.19	1.59	.16*	-.06	-.15*	—											
5. Sel.Jdt	4.16	1.86	-.31**	.16*	.15	-.53**	—										
6. Com.H	5.46	1.92	-.26**	-.03	.15	-.15*	.30**	—									
7. Isol.	5.02	1.55	.00	-.04	.10	-.25**	.32**	-.25**	—								
8. Mind.	8.39	1.45	.18*	-.07	.02	.64**	-.39**	-.07	-.16*	—							
9. Ov.id	3.54	1.49	-.22**	.13	.22**	-.53**	.42**	-.15*	.34**	-.46**	—						
10. Fin.Pr	10.58	3.15	-.31**	.36**	.05	.17*	-.15*	.15*	.00	-.16*	.31**	—					
11. Sc.Ob	25.53	3.57	.32**	-.38**	-.23**	.21**	-.34**	-.27**	-.16*	.22**	-.47**	-.35**	—				
12. Sc.Al	16.16	2.86	.27**	-.43**	-.15*	.20**	-.28**	-.20**	-.02	.30**	-.34**	-.31**	.68**	—			
13. Phy.Ill	0.12	0.33	-.30**	.07	-.07	-.02	.08	.08	.11	.01	.03	.01	.14	-.09	—		
14. Mid.Cl	0.16	0.37	.07	-.17*	-.01	.09	-.08	.10	.05	-.03	-.05	-.16*	-.16*	-.08	.03	—	
15. Gov.Sc	0.16	0.37	-.07	.18*	.11	-.04	.30**	-.03	-.02	-.03	.10	.13	-.11	-.13	-.02	-.15	—

Note. M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation, Phy.Rs=Physical Resources Subscale, Soc.Rs=Social Resources Subscale, Cog.Rs=Cognitive Resources Subscale, Sel.Kd=Self-Kindness Subscale, Sel.Jdt=Self-Judgement Subscale, Com.H=Common Humanity Subscale, Isol=Isolation Subscale, Mind=Mindfulness Subscale, Ov.id=Over-identification Subscale, Fin.Pr=Financial Preparedness Subscale, Sc.Ob=Social Obligation Subscale, Sc.Al=Social Alienation Subscale, Phy.Ill=Physical Illness, Mid.Cl=Middle Class, Gov.Sc=Government Scale. **.p< .01, *.p< .05

The correlation analysis revealed significant relationships between correlates, covariates, and retirement-related outcomes. Physical resources were positively associated with financial preparedness, while social resources were negatively correlated with social obligation and social alienation, indicating stronger support reduces retirement anxiety. Among self-compassion subscales, self-kindness positively correlated with financial preparedness, whereas over-identification was negatively associated with all three retirement anxiety outcomes, highlighting its maladaptive nature. Common humanity was negatively associated with social alienation, and mindfulness was positively correlated with financial preparedness and negatively with social obligation and social alienation. Regarding covariates, middle-class status was negatively correlated with all three retirement anxiety outcomes, physical illness was negatively associated with financial preparedness, and government scale was negatively related to social alienation.

Mediation Analysis

Mediation analysis examines whether the effect of an independent variable (X) on a dependent variable (Y) occurs through a mediator (M), clarifying the mechanism by estimating direct and indirect effects (Hayes, 2018). The analysis was conducted using PROCESS Macro 5.0 in SPSS with bootstrapping. In this study, mediation analyses examined whether self-compassion components mediated the relationships between retirement resources subscales (Physical, Social, Cognitive) and pre-retirement anxiety dimensions (Financial Preparedness, Social Obligation, Social Alienation). Nine analyses were conducted, each fulfilling mediation conditions: IV predicted DV, IV predicted mediators, and mediators predicted DV. The first analysis examined Financial Preparedness (Y) and Physical Resources (X) with all self-compassion subscales as mediators.

Table 3.3.1
Self-Compassion mediating Physical Resources and Financial Preparedness related Retirement Anxiety (N=170)

Consequent		M ₁ (SK)			M ₂ (SJ)			M ₃ (CH)			M ₄ (Isol)			M ₅ (MF)			M ₆ (OI)			Y (FP)								
		B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p						
Antecedent																												
X (PR)	a ₁	.16*	.02	.04	a ₂	-.31***	.03	.00	a ₃	-.26***	.03	.00	a ₄	.00	.02	.10	a ₅	.18*	.02	.02	a ₆	-.22**	.02	.00	c'	-.23**	.05	.00
M ₁ (SK)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₁	.27*	.21	.01
M ₂ (SJ)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₂	.08	.15	.41
M ₃ (CH)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₃	.03	.13	.72
M ₄ (Isol)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₄	-.08	.17	.35
M ₅ (MF)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₅	-.11	.20	.23
M ₆ (OI)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₆	.34***	.19	.00
Constant	i ₁	6.70***	.74	.00	i ₂	7.57***	.83	.00	i ₃	8.40***	.87	.00	i ₄	5.02***	.73	.00	i ₅	6.80***	.67	.00	i ₆	5.49***	.68	.00	i _b	10.07**	2.97	.00
		R ² =.03 F(1, 168) = 4.22, p = .04			R ² =.09 F(1, 168) = 17.30, p < .001			R ² =.07 F(1, 168) = 11.65, p = .00			R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.00, p = .10			R ² =.03 F(1, 168) = 5.76, p = .02			R ² =.05 F(1, 168) = 8.40, p = .00			R ² =.20 F(7, 162) = 5.67, p < .001								

Note. PR=Physical Resources Subscale, SK=Self-Kindness Subscale, SJ=Self-Judgement Subscale, CH=Common Humanity Subscale, Isol=Isolation Subscale, MF=Mindfulness Subscale, OI=Over-identification Subscale, FP=Financial Preparedness Subscale, Cont=Constant, CI=Confidence Interval. **.p< .01, *.p< .05, ***.p< .001

Total Indirect Effect: β = .050*, BootSE = .028, 95% CI [-.109, -.001]

Table 3.4.1 shows a significant total effect of physical resources (PR) on financial preparedness (FP). The direct effect remained significant, indicating a strong association even after accounting for the mediators. However, the indirect effect was also significant, suggesting that the relationship between PR and FP is partially mediated by specific self-compassion subscales. Among these, self-kindness positively mediated the relationship, while over-

identification showed a significant negative mediation effect. Other mediators did not significantly contribute. This points to both direct and indirect pathways through which PR influences FP.

The second analysis was done with Financial Preparedness as the Y variable and Social Resources as the X variable and all the subscales of Self-Compassion acting as mediators.

Table 3.3.2
Self-Compassion mediating Social Resources and Financial Preparedness related Retirement Anxiety (N=170)

Consequent		M ₁ (SK)			M ₂ (SJ)			M ₃ (CH)			M ₄ (Isol)			M ₅ (MF)			M ₆ (OI)			Y (FP)								
		B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p						
Antecedent																												
X (SR)	<i>a</i> ₁	-.03	.03	.45	<i>a</i> ₂	.08*	.04	.04	<i>a</i> ₃	-.02	.04	.70	<i>a</i> ₄	-.02	.03	.58	<i>a</i> ₅	-.03	.03	.39	<i>a</i> ₆	.05	.03	.09	<i>c'</i>	.27***	.06	.00
M ₁ (SK)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₁	.53**	.20	.01	
M ₂ (SJ)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₂	.09	.15	.54	
M ₃ (CH)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₃	.19	.13	.15	
M ₄ (Isol)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₄	-.07	.17	.69	
M ₅ (MF)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₅	-.30	.20	.13	
M ₆ (OI)		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₆	.67***	.19	.00	
Cont	<i>i</i> ₁	8.63***	.59	.00	<i>i</i> ₂	2.77***	.68	.00	<i>i</i> ₃	5.73***	.72	.00	<i>i</i> ₄	5.34***	.58	.00	<i>i</i> ₅	8.84***	.54	.00	<i>i</i> ₆	2.63***	.55	.00	<i>i</i> _b	5.28***	1.10	.00
		R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.58, p = .45			R ² =.03 F(1, 168) = 4.39, p = .04			R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.15, p = .70			R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.31, p = .58			R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.73, p = .39			R ² =.02 F(1, 168) = 2.83, p = .09			R ² =.25 F(7, 162) = 7.51, p < .001								

Note. SR=Social Resources Subscale, SK=Self-Kindness Subscale, SJ=Self-Judgement Subscale, CH=Common Humanity Subscale, Isol=Isolation Subscale, MF=Mindfulness Subscale, OI=Over-identification Subscale, FP=Financial Preparedness Subscale, Cont=Constant, CI=Confidence Interval. **.p< .01, *.p< .05, ***.p< .001.

Total Indirect Effect: β = .035, BootSE = .030, 95% CI [-.021, .100]

Table 3.4.2 shows the total and direct effects of social resources (SR) on financial preparedness (FP) were significant, indicating a strong relationship independent of the mediators. The overall indirect effect was not significant, suggesting limited mediation. Though over-identification had a potentially meaningful indirect contribution, none of the mediators reached significance individually. Thus, the association between SR and FP appears predominantly direct, with not significant mediation by self-compassion.

The third analysis was conducted with the same Y variable Financial Preparedness and Cognitive Resources as the X variable with all the subscales of Self-Compassion as mediators.

Table 3.3.3
Self-Compassion mediating Cognitive Resources and Financial Preparedness related Retirement Anxiety (N=170)

Consequent		M ₁ (SK)			M ₂ (SJ)			M ₃ (CH)			M ₄ (Isol)			M ₅ (MF)			M ₆ (OI)			Y (FP)								
		B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p						
X (CR)	<i>a</i> ₁	-.04*	.02	.05	<i>a</i> ₂	.05	.02	.05	<i>a</i> ₃	.05	.02	.03	<i>a</i> ₄	.02	.02	-.00	<i>a</i> ₅	.08	.02	.05**	<i>c'</i>	-.00	.04	.95				
M ₁ (SK)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₁	.58**	.21	.01			
M ₂ (SJ)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₂	.23	.16	.06			
M ₃ (CH)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₃	.11	.14	.05			
M ₄ (Isol)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₄	-.20	.18	.07			
M ₅ (MF)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₅	-.29	.21	.07			
M ₆ (OI)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₆	.78***	.20	.00			
Cont	<i>i</i> ₁	9.65***	.75	.00	<i>i</i> ₂	2.47**	.87	.00	<i>i</i> ₃	3.76***	.90	.00	<i>i</i> ₄	4.09***	.73	.00	<i>i</i> ₅	8.54***	.69	.00	<i>i</i> ₆	1.55*	.69	.02	<i>i</i> _b	9.55***	1.49	.00
		R ² =.02 F(1, 168) = 3.95, p = .05			R ² =.02 F(1, 168) = 3.84, p = .05			R ² =.02 F(1, 168) = 3.65, p = .06			R ² =.01 F(1, 168) = 1.68, p = .20			R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.05, p = .82			R ² =.05 F(1, 168) = 8.60, p = .00			R ² =.15 F(7, 162) = 4.18, p < .001								

Note. CR=Cognitive Resources Subscale, SK=Self-Kindness Subscale, SJ=Self-Judgement Subscale, CH=Common Humanity Subscale, Isol=Isolation Subscale, MF=Mindfulness Subscale, OI=Over-identification Subscale, FP=Financial Preparedness Subscale, Cont=Constant, CI=Confidence Interval. **.p<.01, *.p<.05, ***.p<.001.

Total Indirect Effect: $\beta = .030$, BootSE = .025, 95% CI [-.007, .090]

Table 3.4.3 shows that Cognitive Resources (CR) did not demonstrate a significant total or direct effect on Financial Preparedness (FP), indicating a weak overall association between the two variables. However, the total indirect effect was marginally significant, with over-identification emerging as a significant mediator. This suggests that while CR may not directly influence FP, its impact may be conveyed indirectly through self-critical emotional processes, particularly the tendency to over-identify with negative thoughts or emotions. These findings are indicative of an indirect-only (full) mediation, wherein the effect of CR on FP appears to be transmitted entirely through the mediating role of over-identification.

The fourth analysis was conducted with the next subscale of retirement anxiety Social Obligation as Y variable and Physical Resources as the X variable with the same subscales of Self-Compassion as mediators.

Table 3.3.4
Self-Compassion mediating Physical Resources and Social Obligation related Retirement Anxiety (N=170)

Consequent		M ₁ (SK)			M ₂ (SJ)			M ₃ (CH)			M ₄ (Isol)			M ₅ (MF)			M ₆ (OI)			Y (SO)								
		B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p						
X (PR)	a ₁	.05*	.02	.04	a ₂	-.12***	.03	.00	a ₃	-.09**	.03	.00	a ₄	.00	.02	.10	a ₅	.05*	.02	.02	a ₆	-.06**	.02	.00	c'	.12*	.05	.01
M ₁ (SK)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₁	-.33	.22	.13
M ₂ (SJ)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₂	-.23	.17	.18
M ₃ (CH)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₃	-.31*	.14	.03
M ₄ (Isol)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₄	-.13	.18	.45
M ₅ (MF)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₅	.08	.21	.72
M ₆ (OI)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	b ₆	-.96***	.20	.00
Cont	i ₁	6.70***	.74	.00	i ₂	7.57***	.83	.00	i ₃	8.40***	.87	.00	i ₄	5.02***	.73	.00	i ₅	6.80***	.67	.00	i ₆	5.49***	.68	.00	i _b	18.57**	1.59	.00
		R ² =.03 F(1, 168) = 4.22, p = .04			R ² =.09 F(1, 168) = 17.30, p = .00			R ² =.07 F(1, 168) = 11.65, p = .00			R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.00, p = .10			R ² =.03 F(1, 168) = 5.76, p = .02			R ² =.05 F(1, 168) = 8.40, p = .00			R ² =.31 F(7, 162) = 10.52, p < .001								

Note. PR=Physical Resources Subscale, SK=Self-Kindness Subscale, SJ=Self-Judgement Subscale, CH=Common Humanity Subscale, Isol=Isolation Subscale, MF=Mindfulness Subscale, OI=Over-identification Subscale, SO=Social Obligation Subscale, Cont=Constant, CI=Confidence Interval. **.p< .01, *.p< .05, ***.p< .001.

Total Indirect Effect: $\beta = .100$, BootSE = .040, 95% CI [.033, .187]

Table 3.4.4 significant total effect was observed from physical resources (PR) to social obligation (SO), with the direct effect remaining significant. The indirect effect was also significant, suggesting partial mediation. Over-identification negatively mediated the relationship, while other self-compassion components such as common humanity contributed weakly. These findings highlight that PR influences SO both directly and through the pathway of mediation as well.

The next analysis kept Y variable as Social Obligation with Social Resources as X variable and Self-Compassion subscales as mediators.

Table 3.3.5
Self-Compassion mediating Social Resources and Social Obligation related Retirement Anxiety (N=170)

Consequent		M ₁ (SK)			M ₂ (SJ)			M ₃ (CH)			M ₄ (Isol)			M ₅ (MF)			M ₆ (OI)			Y (SO)								
		B	SE	p	B	SE	P	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p						
X (SR)	<i>a</i> ₁	-.03	.03	.45	<i>a</i> ₂	-.08*	.04	.04	<i>a</i> ₃	-.02	.07	<i>a</i> ₄	-.02	.05	.38	<i>a</i> ₅	-.03	.03	<i>a</i> ₆	.05	.03	.09	<i>c'</i>	-.33***	.06	.00		
M ₁ (SK)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₁	-.32	.20	.12		
M ₂ (SJ)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₂	-.15	.16	.35		
M ₃ (CH)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₃	-.47***	.13	.00		
M ₄ (Isol)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₄	-.25	.17	.14		
M ₅ (MF)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₅	.13	.20	.51		
M ₆ (OI)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₆	-.88***	.19	.00		
Cont	<i>i</i> ₁	8.63***	.59	.00	<i>i</i> ₂	2.76***	.68	.00	<i>i</i> ₃	5.73***	.72	.00	<i>i</i> ₄	5.34***	.58	.00	<i>i</i> ₅	8.84***	.54	.00	<i>i</i> ₆	2.63***	.55	.00	<i>i</i> _b	31.97**	1.23	.00
		R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.58, p = .45			R ² =.03 F(1, 168) = 4.39, p = .04			R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.15, p = .70			R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.31, p = .58			R ² =.00 F(1, 168) = 0.73, p = .39			R ² =.02 F(1, 168) = 2.83, p = .09			R ² =.39 F(7, 162) = 14.98, p < .001								

Note. SR=Social Resources Subscale, SK=Self-Kindness Subscale, SJ=Self-Judgement Subscale, CH=Common Humanity Subscale, Isol=Isolation Subscale, MF=Mindfulness Subscale, OI=Over-identification Subscale, SO=Social Obligation Subscale, Cont=Constant, CI=Confidence Interval. **.p< .01, *.p< .05, ***.p< .001.

Total Indirect Effect: $\beta = -.041$, BootSE = .049, 95% CI [-.142, .052]

Table 3.4.5 demonstrated a mediation analysis was conducted to examine whether components of self-compassion mediated the relationship between Social Resources (SR) and Social Obligation (SO). Results showed that higher levels of SR were associated with lower levels of SO, and this relationship remained significant after including all self-compassion components as mediators, indicating partial mediation. However, the total indirect effect was not statistically significant, and none of the individual mediators showed significant indirect effects. Among them, over-identification appeared to contribute the most, though its effect was not significant. These findings suggest that while SR plays an important role in reducing social obligation anxiety, this effect is not substantially mediated by self-compassion components in the present model.

The next analysis also kept Y variable as Social Obligation with Cognitive Resources as X variable and Self-Compassion subscales as mediators.

Table 3.3.6
Self-Compassion mediating Cognitive Resources and Social Obligation related Retirement Anxiety (N=170)

Consequent		M ₁ (SK)			M ₂ (SJ)			M ₃ (CH)			M ₄ (Isol)			M ₅ (MF)			M ₆ (OI)			Y (SO)				
		B	S	p	B	S	p	B	S	p	B	S	p	B	S	p	B	S	p	B	SE	p		
X (CR)	<i>a</i> ₁	-.04*	.025	<i>a</i> ₂	.05	.025	<i>a</i> ₃	.05	.025	<i>a</i> ₄	.03	.025	<i>a</i> ₅	-.00	.025	.08	<i>a</i> ₆	.05**	.025	<i>c</i> ₁	-.07	.04	.10	
M ₁ (SK)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₁	-.41	.22	.07
M ₂ (SJ)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₂	-.31	.17	.07
M ₃ (CH)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₃	-.34*	.14	.02
M ₄ (Isol)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₄	-.08	.18	.05
M ₅ (MF)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₅	.17	.22	.04
M ₆ (OI)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₆	-.96***	.20	.00
Cont	<i>i</i> ₁	9.65***	.75	<i>i</i> ₂	2.47**	.87	<i>i</i> ₃	3.76***	.90	<i>i</i> ₄	4.09***	.73	<i>i</i> ₅	8.54***	.69	<i>i</i> ₆	1.55*	.69	<i>i</i> _b	30.47**	1.65	1.65	.00	
		R ² =.02			R ² =.02			R ² =.02			R ² =.01			R ² =.00			R ² =.05				R ² =.30			
		F(1, 168) = 3.95,			F(1, 168) = 3.84,			F(1, 168) = 3.65,			F(1, 168) = 1.68,			F(1, 168) = 0.05,			F(1, 168) = 8.60,				F(7, 162) = 9.81,			
		p = .05			p = .05			p = .06			p = .20			p = .82			p = .00				p < .001			

Note. CR=Cognitive Resources Subscale, SK=Self-Kindness Subscale, SJ=Self-Judgement Subscale, CH=Common Humanity Subscale, Isol=Isolation Subscale, MF=Mindfulness Subscale, OI=Over-identification Subscale, SO=Social Obligation Subscale, Cont=Constant, CI=Confidence Interval. **.p< .01, *.p< .05, ***.p< .001.

Total Indirect Effect: $\beta = -.067^*$, BootSE = .035, 95% CI [-.150, -.013]

Table 3.4.6 shows that Cognitive resources (CR) had a significant total effect on social obligation (SO), but the direct effect lost significance once mediators were included, pointing to full mediation. The total indirect effect was significant, with over-identification emerging as a significant negative mediator. Other self-compassion variables did not significantly mediate the relationship. This suggests that CR affects SO primarily through over-identification. The next analysis was conducted with Social Alienation as Y variable and Physical Resources as X variable and mediators were all the subscales of Self-Compassion.

Table 3.3.7
Self-Compassion mediating Physical Resources and Social Alienation related Retirement Anxiety (N=170)

Consequent		M ₁ (SK)			M ₂ (SJ)			M ₃ (CH)			M ₄ (Isol)			M ₅ (MF)			M ₆ (OI)			Y (SA)									
		B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p	B	SE	p							
X (PR)	<i>a</i> ₁	.05*	.02	.04	<i>a</i> ₂	-.11***	.02	.00	<i>a</i> ₃	-.09**	.03	.00	<i>a</i> ₄	.00	.02	.10	<i>a</i> ₅	.05*	.02	.02	<i>a</i> ₆	-.06**	.02	.00	<i>c'</i>	.08	.04	.07	
M ₁ (SK)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₁	-.28	.19	.13	
M ₂ (SJ)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₂	-.21	.14	.15	
M ₃ (CH)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₃	-.10	.12	.42	
M ₄ (Isol)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₄	.17	.15	.29	
M ₅ (MF)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₅	.42*	.18	.02	
M ₆ (OI)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₆	-.50**	.17	.00	
Cont	<i>i</i> ₁	6.70***	.74	.00	<i>i</i> ₂	7.57***	.83	.00	<i>i</i> ₃	8.40***	.87	.00	<i>i</i> ₄	5.02***	.73	.00	<i>i</i> ₅	6.80***	.67	.00	<i>i</i> ₆	5.49***	.68	.00	<i>i</i> _b	11.55**	1.30	.00	
		R ² =.03				R ² =.09				R ² =.07				R ² =.00				R ² =.03			R ² =.05				R ² =.21				
		F(1, 168) = 4.22,				F(1, 168) = 17.30,				F(1, 168) = 11.65,				F(1, 168) = 0.00,				F(1, 168) = 5.76,			F(1, 168) = 8.40,				F(7, 162) = 6.05,				
		p = .04				p = .00				p = .00				p = .10					p = .02			p = .00				p < .001			

Note. PR=Physical Resources Subscale, SK=Self-Kindness Subscale, SJ=Self-Judgement Subscale, CH=Common Humanity Subscale, Isol=Isolation Subscale, MF=Mindfulness Subscale, OI=Over-identification Subscale, SA=Social Alienation Subscale, Cont=Constant, CI=Confidence Interval. **.p< .01, *.p< .05, ***.p< .001.

Total Indirect Effect: $\beta = .070^*$, BootSE = .027, 95% CI [.027, .133]

Table 3.4.7 shows that the relationship between Physical Resources (PR) on Social Alienation (SA) was not statistically significant when assessed through the total effect, although the overall mediation model was significant. The direct effect of PR on SA was marginal, suggesting a weak direct association. Among the components of self-compassion, mindfulness showed a significant positive effect on SA, whereas over-identification demonstrated a significant negative effect and emerged as a significant mediator in the model. This indicates a suppressing or inconsistent mediation effect and highlight the role of self-critical emotional tendencies in complicating the otherwise protective impact of physical resources on social alienation.

The next analysis was conducted with Social Alienation as Y variable and Social Resources as X variable and mediators were all the subscales of Self-Compassion.

The analysis revealed a significant total effect of social resources (SR) on social alienation (SA), indicating that lower perceived social resources are associated with higher levels of social alienation related retirement anxiety. The direct effect remained significant even after accounting for the mediating variables, suggesting that SR independently predicts SA. However, the total indirect effect was not significant, indicating that the collective contribution of the self-compassion subscales as mediators was weak. None of the individual self-compassion variables, significantly mediated the relationship between SR and SA. These findings suggest that while SR is an important predictor of SA, this relationship operates primarily through a direct path rather than being substantially explained by self-compassion.

The next analysis was conducted with Social Alienation as Y variable and Cognitive Resources as X variable and mediators were all the subscales of Self-Compassion.

Table 3.4.8 showed the total effect of cognitive resources (CR) on social alienation (SA) was marginally significant, while the direct effect became non-significant after including the mediators, suggesting possible indirect influence. Although the overall indirect effect was not significant, over-identification showed a near-significant negative mediation effect. This indicates that CR may influence SA through self-critical processes like over-identification, rather than through a direct pathway. Other self-compassion variables did not significantly mediate this relationship.

Figure 3.1

Summary of the Findings

The main findings indicated acceptable internal consistency for most scales, with the Retirement Resources Inventory showing satisfactory to good reliability, the Retirement Anxiety Scale demonstrating acceptable overall reliability, and the Self-Compassion Scale showing modest but usable reliability for exploratory research. Correlation analysis revealed that physical and social resources were associated with lower retirement anxiety, while self-kindness and mindfulness were positively related to better retirement outcomes and over-identification showed negative associations across anxiety dimensions. Some demographic variables, including middle-class status and physical illness, were significantly related to retirement anxiety. Mediation analyses showed that self-compassion partially mediated several relationships, particularly through self-kindness and over-identification, while some relationships were mainly direct, suggesting that both retirement resources and self-compassion play critical roles in retirement-related anxiety.

Discussion

This research examined the contribution of retirement resources and self-compassion in explaining retirement anxiety among pre-retirees, focusing on how physical, cognitive, and social resources relate to financial preparedness, social obligation, and social alienation, and how self-compassion mediates these relationships. Using hierarchical regression and mediation analyses, the study advances understanding of psychological vulnerability and resilience during retirement transition and provides empirical support for the buffering role of self-compassion. The findings support the Resource-Based Dynamic Model of Retirement Adjustment (Wang et al., 2011), showing that higher physical and social resources predicted greater financial preparedness and lower social obligation and alienation, consistent with prior research (Leung & Earl, 2012; Topa et al., 2018). Physical resources were particularly important, supporting earlier findings on health, autonomy, and reduced stress (Kim & Moen, 2002), while social resources aligned with Antonucci's Convoy Model of Social Relations (Antonucci et al., 2010). Cognitive resources showed weak direct effects but significant

indirect effects through self-compassion, particularly over-identification (Earl et al., 2015). Mediation analyses indicated that self-kindness and over-identification played key roles, with over-identification consistently emerging as a maladaptive mediator (Raes, 2010; Allen et al., 2012), while self-kindness facilitated better financial preparedness. Although common humanity and mindfulness showed weaker mediation effects, correlation findings suggest potential contextual benefits (Geiger et al., 2016). Overall, the results align with Compassionate Mind Theory (Gilbert, 2009) and extend its relevance to retirement. Demographic factors such as middle-class status and physical illness were linked to greater insecurity, consistent with socioeconomic and health literature (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014; Kim & Moen, 2002). Practically, the findings emphasize integrating self-compassion training into retirement planning interventions, particularly for individuals with limited external resources.

Conclusion

The study highlights the importance of both external and internal resources in preparing individuals for retirement. Physical, social, and cognitive resources predicted key dimensions of retirement anxiety, while self-compassion—especially self-kindness and over-identification—played an influential mediating role. These findings suggest that alongside tangible resources, internal psychological processes meaningfully shape how individuals perceive and prepare for retirement.

Strengths of the Study

- Retirement-related psychological challenges, particularly retirement anxiety, remain insufficiently explored in many cultural contexts, and this study contributes valuable data to an often overlooked topic in research and practice.
- As most retirement studies are conducted in Western settings, the present study adds cultural relevance by examining retirement anxiety in a non-Western, collectivistic society where social and financial conditions differ significantly.
- The study employed structured mediation analysis to examine both direct and indirect

pathways between retirement resources and retirement anxiety, providing deeper insight into underlying psychological mechanisms.

- Focusing on pre-retirement individuals addressed a timely and underexplored phase, increasing relevance for early intervention and planning strategies.
- Separate analysis of subscales of retirement resources, self-compassion, and retirement anxiety allowed a nuanced understanding of their unique contributions to retirement outcomes.

Limitations and Suggestions

- The sample, though adequate in size, was not equally diverse across demographic categories such as age groups, income levels, or employment sectors; future research should aim for more demographically balanced samples to better reflect the broader pre-retirement population.
- The study relied solely on self-report questionnaires, which may introduce biases such as social desirability and inaccurate self-perception; future research could incorporate multiple data sources, such as behavioral measures or reports from peers or professionals, to enhance accuracy and validity.

Implications of the Study

- The findings highlight the role of self-compassion, particularly self-kindness and reduced over-identification, in improving retirement readiness, suggesting these aspects can be targeted in psychological or counseling programs to support individuals emotionally.
- Physical, social, and cognitive resources significantly influenced retirement anxiety outcomes, indicating that pre-retirement planning programs should address not only financial matters but also broader personal and environmental resources.
- The results imply that psychological and emotional readiness for retirement is as important as financial preparedness, and employers, HR departments, and policymakers should integrate emotional

wellbeing components into retirement preparation frameworks.

- Individuals with low self-compassion or limited social and cognitive resources may be more vulnerable to retirement anxiety, providing a basis for early screening and tailored support strategies in organizational or clinical settings.

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